

Philosophy and Practices of Science: A Scientific Overview of the Sāṅkhya Philosophy

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Author:

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma

Email: kksharma69@yahoo.com

Corresponding Address:

C-7, Bank Men Colony, Kankarbagh,
Patna-800020, Bihar (India).
Contact: 9504782781.

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Abstract

This paper reviews various scientific practices and try to evaluate them certain philosophical theories of science, such as demarcation, under determination, falsification, induction, realism, and anti-realism. There were a great degree of variation between the scientific theories and practices has been found. Most of the scientific theories did not prove to be realistic, however they mere appeared inductive in nature. The deficiencies in various scientific approached were evident as they repeatedly failed in portraying a wholesome picture of creation. Contrary to that the *Sāṅkhya* has provided a better conceivable description of the creation. Therefore, it was required from the scientific communities to adopt those methods of study while deducting.

Key words: *Philosophy of Science; Philosophical Conflict in Scientific Practices; Sāṅkhya Philosophy; Creation.*

Introduction:

The *Sāṅkhya* system of Indian Philosophy believed as pronounced by Sage *Kapila* is believed to be the most primitive among all the six orthodox schools of Indian Philosophy because of the fact that the period of *Kapila* could be even dated back to those *Upanishads* and *Epics* periods. The system appeared purely scientific that considered creation (*Shristi*) as an effect that caused due to assimilation between the *Puruṣa* and *Prakriti*. It further said about *Puruṣa* and *Prakriti* as opposite to each other and could term as paradoxical duals that always remained associated with each other and never separate, and could only separate during the rollback of creation called *Pralaya*. Therefore, both together considered as the root cause of creation.

Every particle or matter though a maker of unintelligent *Prakriti*, however, behaved intelligently due to presence of conscious *Puruṣa*. Further, the *guna* or properties of matter were three ie *Sattva*, *Rajas*, and *Tamas*. The heterogeneous and homogenous motions of *Sattva*, *Rajas*, and *Tamas* could be the root cause of actions, reactions, and effects all-round.

Why the modern science failed to create a wholesome picture? The reason is obvious that they did not adopt the appropriate approach of study or requirement of certain falsifiable standards made them redundant and felt deficient in arranging those tools and techniques. The enormity of the universe may be another reason whereby testing of hypothesis cannot be repeated in on such a large or so called infinite object of study.

The philosophy of science until 1990 has been mainly dominated by physicists and their main works remained based upon certain induction be it either *Newton* or *Einstein*. Contrary to physics, chemistry appeared to be more realistic, however, chemists remained largely preoccupied in synthesis of materials they found useful for them. Chemists also fail while making analysis as they also suffer due to deficiency of ideas while making an analysis. Chemists discovered so many molecules and even faced great difficulties in logical nomenclature. Even the periodic table suffered with great degree of induction and insufficiency. In addition, the very structure of molecules, chemical bonding, and the distinction made between atoms, electrons, protons and other sub nuclear particles remained largely tentative that could not be termed as a work of scientists.

Full Text:

The philosophy of science has already suffered due to lack of participation of chemical scientists that has resulted in lack of qualitative and quantitative data on numerous issues. There has been growing realization that chemical concepts could not be deduced from quantum mechanical principles. Chemistry needed its own philosophy as a number of French philosophers – Pierre Duhem, Émile Meyerson, Hélène Metzger – have paved the way for such an approach. In particular, Gaston Bachelard has suggested an alternative philosophy that he termed “metachemistry”. The contemporary science cannot be restricted to the continuation of the past.

Any philosophical examination of chemistry should take into account the fact that chemistry is and always has been a laboratory science. The problems and objects of study of chemistry have been provided by and limited by the operations that could be performed on materials in a chemical laboratory. Chemists attempt to know substances by transforming them by means of manipulations and physical operations. Whatever the importance of chemical theory, chemistry is first and foremost concerned with making. Historically, it was an art and craft before it became an academic science. The reliable knowledge gained of the molecular world came from the hot and the cool work of our hands and mind combined.

In medieval times, chemists tested everything with fire, but since then they have come to use all sorts of chemical reactants and physical techniques of measurement, ranging from traditional balances, hydrometers, gasometers, to modern spectrometers. In 1787, when a group of French academicians designed a “method for naming”, they assumed that by formulating the major requirements for a chemical nomenclature, they would provide subsequent generations with reliable guidelines for naming any newly discovered substances. They formulated general rules for coining systematic names based on composition, and banished names based on the substance’s qualities, its uses, or the circumstances of its discovery. In doing so, they were acting as ‘architects of matter’, designing and planning future chemical edifices.

In the words of Dr. S. Radha Krishnan “Science tries to sort out, whereas philosophy tries to sum up”. Further, he has also termed philosophy as the science of the science and master science (Radhakrishnan, 1932).

There was a tremendous development of the science in the ancient India. The advancement in the field of mathematics, astronomy, metallurgy, architecture and even study of matter were almost complete and still puzzled the scientific communities that how this knowledge were acquired. Even there are publications terming that this knowledge were provided to ancient

Indians by aliens. However, it is a proven fact that all those knowledge were accessed by a great application of mind as they are still preserved in those vast ancient literatures in the Sanskrit language and various digest and commentary, and translations over them are also available to us. The ancient Vedic hymns were not without a scientific basis, however based upon a total knowledge. However, it has been made to realize that those ancient texts are mere an object of chanting in religious occasions and temples (Katzu, 2009).

Still, it could appear surprising that how ancient people said so much accurately about creation, order of evolution, time, space, dimension and direction. The methods of study and cognition of knowledge in ancient India appeared quite different from the modern science, however they became precise and capable of describing facts without any scientific experiments.

Sāṅkhya system appeared predominantly intellectual that advocated the right knowledge would cause separation of *Puruṣa* from *Prakriti*. *Sāṅkhya* considered *Prakriti* as the root cause of the world of objects. Further *Prakriti* defined as uncaused, unmanifested, unintelligent and ever active yet all worlds and its objects contained in its bosom. *Prakriti* said to be the unity of three *guna* or properties defined as *Sattva*, *Rajas* and *Tamas* (Sharma D. C., 2009).

Sattva, literary meant real or existent and considered responsible for the manifestation of objects in consciousness. It referred as goodness and produced pleasure. It's regarded as light and bright, buoyant, and illuminating. It also further said that the luminosity of light, power of reflections, upward movements, pleasure, happiness, contentment, and bliss all due to it. Its color described as white.

Rajas, literary meant foulness termed as the principle of motion. It produced pain, restless activity, feverish efforts, and wild stimulation. It usually remained mobile and its color as red.

Tamas, literary meant darkness termed as a principle of inertia. It produced apathy and indifference. Ignorance, sloth, confusion, bewilderment, passivity and negativity could be its consequences. It termed heavy and enveloping and such oppressed to *Sattva*. It also opposed to *Rajas* as it could arrest activity. Its color said as dark.

Those three *guna* that constituted *Prakriti* never separated. They could conflict and yet cooperate with one another and always found intermingled. If all those properties held in equilibrium, nothing happened. The predominance of one *guna* over other disturbs the equilibrium. When heterogeneous motion started, *Rajas* disturbed the equilibrium. The heterogeneous and

homogenous motions of *gunās* held responsible for the creation and rollback of creation that means a cessation of creation, whereby a matter ultimately devoid of its properties or *gunās*.

Sāṅkhya philosophy further said about 24 numerals make of *Prakṛiti* that constituted the entire creation, excluding *Puruṣa*, being the twenty-fifth. However, the *Parmātmā* that so far could not be a subject of the science controlled both. The intelligent *Puruṣa* and unintelligent *Prakṛiti* combined to cause living and non-living matter. The *Puruṣa* and *Prakṛiti* could not separate from each other however; they separated at the time of roll back of creation called *Pralaya*.

2. Questions:

Science still faced difficulties in describing several phenomena such as it could say nothing about how matter or particle acted intelligently without any brain. Further, how a matter exhibited different properties under different circumstances. Different living creatures, why showed similar or different emotions in any particular situations. Science still puzzles why some material is lighter and heavier? What is the mystery of dark matter or energy? Why matter changes its form? Why gender demarcation happened?

3. Findings:

The *Puruṣa* and *Prakṛiti* of *Sāṅkhya* were almost sufficient cause for creation. They differed in qualities because *Puruṣa* was all consciousness and intelligent, whereas *Prakṛiti* was unintelligent and it was not possible for her to cause anything without the *Puruṣa*. In fact, *Prakṛiti* could never act alone, however; it used to serve the purpose of all conscious *Puruṣa*. Due to *Puruṣa* there could exist a unified field of consciousness that connected every matter living or nonliving. Every matter or particle worked in accordance serving the mutual interests for continuance of existence and that could be the reason that every matter or particle exhibited a particular quality in different circumstances.

At the behest of God, there is a merger of Puruṣa and Prakṛiti that started the series of cause, causation, and caused. Those events were followed by sequenced Evolutes appearing on an order. As the Space was the first evolute followed respectively by Ether, Air, Fire, Water and Earth. All the 24 numerals of Sāṅkhya consecutively caused in order as a material cause. Sāṅkhya clearly stated that the three gunas could be the reason of any matter being lighter or heavier. Further, it could say that dark energy could be a manifestation of predomination Tamas. Rise of dark matter could cause more and more destruction. The vibrations of Sattas, Rajas and Tamas resulted in cyclic order of creation and recreations. One guna could predominate, assimilate or

annihilate other *guna*. The three *gunas* remained intermingled with each other like a rope and could never separate from each other until the *Pralay* or the rollback of the creation. God himself gets caused and entered the creation started by them and make his presence in every particle. Matter changes its form due to the ever active three *gunas* over it and therefore continuous change could be the main attribution of this whole creation.

India was probably the first civilization to study matter in terms of gender and therefore several matters termed as masculine while many as feminine. The whole grammar in different Indian languages, including ancient Sanskrit took account of gender of not the living however nonliving matters also. The intelligent, long lasting or stable matter in nature generally assigned masculine gender. The temporary, ever active, and unintelligent materials assigned feminine gender. Most powerful materials assigned feminine gender because a power usually short lived and transforms so quickly however after causing the effects. A whole range of grammar in Hindi, Sanskrit and many other Indian languages developed based upon such gender demarcation. However, gender demarcation started in the living world at its onset whereby *Brhamā* took birth as *Ubhayalingi* (*Hermaphrodite*) that means both masculine and feminine systems within one body. The duty of *Brhamā* to expand the creation, however he failed in his first attempt because he produced four materials (*Sanat, Sanadan* etc..) that were not able to sustain further and carry forward as they get confused because of having similar properties as being *Hermaphrodites*. Therefore, the *Brahmā* intelligently divided his body in two parts, one was male and another was female. Such demarcation was also found in many plants. However, still there are *Hermaphrodite* among animals and plants, and they may be descendants of those initial four creations of *Brahma*.

Science is repeatedly coming across some very simple questions and they faced difficulties in putting a valid and logical answer. Most of their analysis remained mere a work of intuitivism without any premises. Therefore the lack of deductive approach was very much a case within the scientific community as if the premises would be correct then only the conclusion would be correct. The whole idea of astrology has been rejected by the scientists terming it totally pseudo-science because of being based upon induction and tempting to accept the conclusion correct without any premises or even trying to suggest false premises to justify their conclusions.

On the other hand the astronomy is taught in university because of being based upon certain logic and valid premises.

The concluding remarks of numerous scientists and their theories are being re-examined in the light of those

philosophical foundations and they appeared mere a work of intuitivism. It could not be a work of science to cheat the people in the name of science. The scientific practices in many disciplines have created a situation whereby they denounce a justifiable knowledge in the name of science without any basis. So many diseases surfaced and medicines are prescribed amidst the sole premises of making profit. This is not the work of scientist to mobilize profit using their scientific revelations. The tendency has been growing that every person has been probability of being declared under the grip of certain disease and their scope of living a healthy life has been snatched. The same software companies that make antivirus are also engaged in making virus. The scientific community has lost the ethics and that is required to be imposed. The free flow of scientific knowledge is the root cause of such problems. Even the restriction of knowledge to certain individuals or institutions also creating problems. Rightful knowledge should be possessed by the rightful person and may be utilized in the wellbeing of the all humankind and the universe as a whole.

Conclusion

A philosophy is required for every field of study and human activity. A distinct philosophy is required to guide the human activities including education and research in the field of science, social science, commerce or business. Moreover, it is needed to develop Indian Science, Indian Social Science, and Indian Commerce. It can be done by primary focus and citing works and publications within the Indian ecology of various ancient, medieval, and modern scholars, texts, and publications. In contrast to all other fields of studies the Indian Philosophy has established itself as a distinct and well recognized branch of studies and same needed to be replicated in every field of activities, studies and education. The Indian philosophy has been able to describe the contents far better than those ancient Greeks, and yet they are not quoted preferably due to the hegemony persisted in the education sector. Methods of education and research can be better shaped by way descriptions mentioned in different branches of Indian philosophy.

Indian philosophy do not have any categorization and classification of things and looked an object in a holistic approach. Even in the field of medical science, we could see that there are specialist of every organ or a system in the body. And in this manner, there would be a separate specialist for a left hand and a right hand and so on

Atomism is an area which is under critical review by the scientists. Aristotle insisted that if the components are preserved unchanged, then the next is only apparent. A true mixt is not, therefore, composed of constituents sticking together. Something new is created, with properties not possessed by the original ingredients. The emergence of a new 'stuff' implies that the ingredients, no longer coexist with the mixt. Consequently, a true mixt can be characterized by an *either...or* condition.

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